

**ICCB
2019**

**VIII International Conference on
Computational Bioengineering
4-6 September 2019, Belgrade, Serbia**

ICCB 2019

Proceedings

**8th International Conference on
Computational Bioengineering**

September 4-6, Belgrade, Serbia

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Computational Bioengineering**

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Organizers

University of Kragujevac

University of Belgrade

**Bioengineering Research and
Development Centre BioIRC**

Faculty of Engineering Kragujevac

Supporting organizations

**The Ministry of Education, Science
and Technological Development of
The Republic of Serbia**

European Society of Biomechanics

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Welcome Message

Dear colleagues and students,

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, it is our great pleasure to welcome you to the *8th International Conference on Computational Bioengineering (ICCB2019)* which is taking place in Belgrade, Serbia, from 4th-6th September, 2019.

The ICCB2019 promotes complementary disciplines that hold great promise for the advancement of research and development in complex medical, biological and computer systems. The main conference includes sixteen sections dealing with topics such as biomechanics, cardiovascular engineering, patient-specific modeling, multiscale modelling, data mining, decision support systems, biomaterials and dental biomechanics, nanomedicine, tissue and cell engineering, computational chemistry, sports bioengineering, etc. Within sixteen sections, we also have seven mini symposia dealing with the issues in the fields of artificial intelligence, machine learning, computational chemistry, risk assessment, computational and experimental physiology, augmented reality and multi-scale modelling. The conference is organized, sponsored and supported by the University of Kragujevac, University of Belgrade, Bioengineering Research and Development Center BioIRC, Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia and European Society of Biomechanics.

The ICCB is a large international conference with 16 years of tradition and leading reputation. It follows previous successful conferences held in Spain in 2003, in Portugal in 2005, in Venezuela in 2007, in Italy in 2009, in Belgium in 2013, in Spain in 2015, in France in 2017. ICCB gathers eminent scientists and researchers, as well as students aiming to promote interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary approaches needed for solving complex problems, which requires expertise in the field of biomedical sciences and engineering.

This year, the ICCB 2019 has received more than 150 high-quality research papers and the best papers have been chosen for this Book of Abstracts. Each paper has been reviewed by at least 2 scientists in the program and scientific review committee. As a result of the strict review process and evaluation, the committee has selected papers which will be published as full regular research papers.

We are delighted to announce 10 world renowned scientists as ICCB 2019 keynote speakers:

Dimitrios Fotiadis, University of Ioannina, Greece

Valentin Djonov, University of Bern, Switzerland

Akira Tsuda, HSPH, Harvard University, USA

Marie-Christine Ho Ba Tho, University of Technology of Compiègne, France

Milos Kojic, Houston Methodist Research Institute, USA

Stephane Avril, Center for Biomedical and Healthcare Engineering, France

Nino Russo, Universita della Calabria, Italy

Erik Klein, *University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia*

Julien Barthes, *PROTIP MEDICAL, Strasbourg, France*

Atul Bhaskar, *University of Southampton, UK*

We must also say that the conference would certainly not have been so successful without the efforts of many people who were actively engaged in organization of such a major internationally recognized academic event. We give our special gratitude to the members of the program and scientific review committee as well as to all chairs, organizers and committee members for their dedication and support.

This year, ICCB Conference is held in Belgrade, Serbia, a city with rich cultural heritage and extensive and colorful history. We hope that you will find time to explore the city and experience its soul. Serbia already has a number of very good scientists in the area of bioengineering and ICCB2019 is an excellent opportunity to introduce their research and scientific achievements in these challenging areas.

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, we wish you all a pleasant stay in Belgrade and a productive conference.

Prof. Nenad Filipović, *Conference Program Chair*

Organization and Committees

Local Organization Committee

Nenad Filipovic, University of Kragujevac, (Chairperson)

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M. Viceconti, UK
Yang GZ, UK
Zervakis M, Greece

Program at a Glance

Wednesday 04 September 2019			
08:45 - 09:15	<p style="text-align: center;">Opening Ceremony - Welcome speech:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Dr. Nenad Filipovic, rector of the University of Kragujevac, Conference Chair Dr. Viktor Nedovic, State Secretary, Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development Dr. Berislav Vekic, State Secretary, Ministry of Health</p>		
09:15- 09:45	<p style="text-align: center;">Keynote speaker: Topic: Angiogenesis modeling Prof. Valentin Djonov, University of Bern, Switzerland</p>		
09:45 - 10:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.1 Mini-Symposia 4: COMPUTATIONAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PHYSIOLOGY: NOVEL POTENTIAL ANTINEOPLASTIC COMPOUNDS AND CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM</p>		
10:30 - 11:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Coffee Break</p>		
11:00 - 11:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Keynote speaker: Topic: Nanoparticles, pulmonary medicine Prof. Akira Tsuda, Harvard School of Public Health, Boston, MA, USA</p>		
11:30 – 13:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.2 Mini-Symposia 6: MULTISCALE IN-SILICO MODELING OF CARDIOMYOPATHY FROM GENO TYPE TO PHENO TYPE</p>		
13:00 - 14:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Buffet Lunch</p>		
14:00 - 15:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.3 Biomedical Decision Support System</p>		
15:00 - 15:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Keynote speaker: Topic: In silico and in vitro tissue models for biomaterial risk assessment and tissue engineering Julien Barthes, PROTIP MEDICAL, Strasbourg, France</p>		
15:30 - 16:30	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.4 Mini-Symposia 7: MULTISCALE MODELLING OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA RELATED TO BIOMATERIAL RISK ASSESSMENT (part I)</p>		
16:30 - 17:00	<p style="text-align: center;">Coffee Break</p>		
17:00 - 17:45	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.5 Mini-Symposia 7: MULTISCALE MODELLING OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA RELATED TO BIOMATERIAL RISK ASSESSMENT (part II)</p>		
17:45 – 18:30	<table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; border: none; vertical-align: top;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Session W.6.1 Gene Expression Analysis and Engineering</p> </td> <td style="width: 50%; border: none; vertical-align: top;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Session W.6.2 Mini-Symposia 3: RISK ASSESSMENT IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.6.1 Gene Expression Analysis and Engineering</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.6.2 Mini-Symposia 3: RISK ASSESSMENT IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.6.1 Gene Expression Analysis and Engineering</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Session W.6.2 Mini-Symposia 3: RISK ASSESSMENT IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES</p>		

Thursday 05 September 2019		
08:30 - 09:00	Keynote speaker: Topic: Multiscale modeling Prof. Dimitrios I. Fotiadis, <i>University of Ioannina, Greece</i>	
09:00 – 09:30	Keynote speaker: Topic: Smeared multiscale finite element models for drug delivery and in electrophysiology Prof. Milos Kojic, <i>Houston Methodist Research Institute, USA</i>	
09:30 - 11:00	Session T.1 Computational Modeling	
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee Break	
11:30 – 12:00	Keynote speaker: Topic: Inverse problems in cardiovascular continuum mechanics and medical applications Prof. Stephane Avril, <i>Center for Biomedical and Healthcare Engineering, France</i>	
12:00 – 13:00	Session T.2 Cardiovascular Engineering	
13:00 - 14:00	Buffet Lunch	
14:00 – 16:00	Session T.3.1 Biomechanics (part I)	Session T.3.2 InSilc Workshop
16:00 - 16:30	Coffee Break	
16:30 - 17:00	Keynote speaker: Topic: Theoretical Study of Radical Scavenging Activity of Para-Substituted Phenols Prof. Erik Klein, <i>University of Technology in Bratislava, Slovakia</i>	
17:00 - 18:45	Session T.4 Mini-Symposia 2: APPLIED COMPUTATIONAL CHEMISTRY (part I)	
20:00 - 23:00	Gala Dinner	

Friday 06 September 2019	
08:30 - 09:00	<p>Keynote speaker: Topic: Musculoskeletal system Prof. Marie-Christine Ho Ba Tho, <i>University of Technology of Compiègne, France</i></p>
09:00 – 11:00	<p>Session F.1 Biomechanics (part II)</p>
11:00 - 11:30	Coffee Break
11:30 – 12:30	<p>Session F.2 Mini-Symposia 1: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING IN BIOENGINEERING</p>
12:30 - 13:00	<p>Keynote speaker: Topic: Computational mechanics of implants and scaffolds Prof. Atul Bhaskar, <i>University of Southampton, UK</i></p>
13:00 – 14:00	Buffet Lunch
14:00 - 14:30	<p>Keynote speaker: Topic: Metals in cancer therapy. A computational viewpoint Prof. Nino Russo, <i>Universita della Calabria, Italy</i></p>
14:30 - 16:15	<p>Session F.3 Mini-Symposia 2: APPLIED COMPUTATIONAL CHEMISTRY (part II)</p>
16:15 – 17:15	<p>Session F.4 Signal Processing</p>
17:15 – 17:45	<p>Session F.5 Mini-Symposia 5: HOLOGRAM AND AUGMENTED REALITY BIOMECHANICAL MODELS OF A VIRTUAL BALANCE PHYSIOTHERAPIST AND COGNITIVE TRAINING GAMES</p>
17:45 - 18:15	Closing Ceremony

W.4.1 – Computational immunoprofiling predictions of immune response promiscuity to Epstein Barr Virus epitopes and oral biofilm in acute coronary syndrome - Mariliis Jaago^{1,2}, Arno Pihlak¹, Helle Sadam^{1,2}, Valentina Bozok¹, Oliver Nisumaa³, Jaak Vilo³, Pirkko Pussinen⁴, Nihal Engin Vrana^{5,6}, Kaia Palm^{1,2*}

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Abstract:

The use of biomaterials in clinical applications has increased dramatically over the past decade, as they are implemented as drug delivery vehicles, tissue repair scaffolds, and replacement elements for damaged body parts. However, introducing biomaterials to the body may include inflammation, collateral tissue damage, and thus early loss of function. Today we have no framework of identification of individuals with heightened risk for unfavourable reactions to biomaterials despite that the individuality of immune system features along with the infectious background underlying clinical diagnoses is high. Mimotope Variation Analysis (MVA), a comprehensive immunoprofiling technology based on next generation phage display enables the description of the antibody repertoire of an individual at any given time. In a clinical cohort (n=96) of persons with varying degree of coronary heart disease (stable form, or acute coronary syndrome), and background of gingivitis or periodontitis, MVA immunoprofiling revealed differential immune response against two common antigens of Epstein-Barr virus (EBV), also known as human herpesvirus 4, namely VP26 and EBNA6 across disease groups. VP26-similar regions discovered by MVA analysis were also identified in several bacterial pathogens in oral biofilms and as mimicking epitopes in certain biopolymers with potential to elicit cross-reactive immune response. Our findings support the role of the immune system in the development of the coronary artery disease and propose MVA as a technology of assessing individual's further risk against biomaterials based on the current status of their immune system.

Keywords: immunoprofiling, acute coronary syndrome, biomaterial, implant failure, risk assessment

Acknowledgement: We thank the BIIT group and team of Quretec, Llc. for IT support. Biomaterial samples kindly provided by Protip Medical. The research was funded by the institutional research grant of Protobios (nr 5.1-4/1373) and by personal research grant of KP (PRG578) from the Estonian Research Council. Protobios team was supported by EU H2020 RIA research funding (PanBioRa, EU760921).

W.4.2 – Analysis of Focus Measure and Image Fusion of Microscopy Images - Arban Uka^{1*}, Florenc Skuka², Latif Xeka¹, Harry Esmonde³, Nihal Engin Vrana⁴

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Abstract:

Analysis of health condition of cellular material and the interaction of cells with different biomaterials requires the use of good and efficient image acquisition techniques. In order to mimic the behavior of a biosystem researchers employ use of microfluidic cells and these systems provide a large amount of data. The major expectation for these testing systems is to be portable and fast in acquiring high quality and processing the images. One of important aspects is to have a system that is independent for both tasks. Autofocusing is an important step that requires good control from the imaging module operator. The aim of this work is to evaluate different algorithms that quantify the focus measure metrics and determine the one that is the most efficient in terms of computational runtime and quality of the image. Fourteen different algorithms have been tested for large dataset of microscopy images (both in focus and defocused images) and the most efficient associated metric score is determined. The investigated algorithms are energy of gradient, Gaussian derivative, thresholded gradient, squared gradient, energy of Laplacian, Modified Laplacian, wavelet variance, wavelet ratio, gray-level variance, standard deviation, histogram entropy, histogram range, image curvature and spatial frequency measurement. The most reliable algorithm was chosen the one that reported the largest metric difference between any two images that were close to the best focus. The computational runtime range from the fastest to the slowest has four orders of magnitude difference. The best kernel sizes that are compatible with the inherent characteristics of a microscope image are determined. Determining the fastest algorithm is important as the microscope can be set to acquire several images of regions that are out of focus and then through image fusion all the different sections can be merged to construct a well-focused large image.

Keywords: Autofocusing, microscopy, focus measures, automated microscopy

Acknowledgement: This work received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 760921.

W.4.3 – Mathematical simulation of biodegradable material cytotoxicity in 3D hepatocellular systems in vitro - Alexander Makhaniok¹, Constantin-Edi Tanase², Amir Ghaemmaghami², Nihal Engin Vrana³, Vitaly Goranov^{1*}

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Abstract:

Degradation of implanted materials produces toxic byproducts that can cause cell damage and apoptosis, especially at hepatic level, where hepatocyte “take the first stab” of the circulated toxins. We elaborated own mathematical model taking into account “diffusion mass transfer” to evaluate the kinetics of cell death and estimate the cytotoxicity of the biodegradation products of a degradable material by analysis of in vitro data. These models are applicable in cases when the rate of cell death is proportional to the concentration of the toxic products of bi-materials degradation. The model takes into account the surface area of the material under test and allows predicting the cytotoxicity of the material considering the 3D geometry of hepatocellular spheroids. We have mathematically validated spatial distribution of damaged cells inside the spheroids under the influence of different concentrations of low-toxic products that can be used for distinguishing the direct and indirect (metabolite) toxicity.

Keywords: Ascending thoracic aortic aneurysm, Inverse method, Rupture risk, Finite element

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 760921 (PANBioRA).

W.4.4 – The Mathematical approach to disclose low Cytotoxicity of material from in vitro co-culture experiment - Ivan Siutsou¹, Lydie Ploux², Nihal Engin Vrana², Vitaly Goranov^{1*}

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Abstract:

The problem of low-level (latent) toxicity uncovering is central for evaluation of new biomaterials safety. The developed method allows to estimate relevance of possible toxicity effects by comparison of growth curves in cell culture experiments. It naturally incorporates possible variance of initial conditions and allows it to be distinguished from real toxicity effects. We elaborated the method which includes two-parametric model of cell proliferation with parameters identifiable as basic proliferation rate r and limiting cell density c . Least squares method is used for parameters estimation. As bacterial contamination of the biomaterials and the potential interactions between biomaterials and microbiota are also important factors to analyse, such models can be also used to predict bacterial growth in the presence of biomaterials and mammalian cells for a given application.

The method was tested on the data of *E. coli* K12 proliferation on surfaces of osteoblastic cells (STRO) and free surfaces of biocompatible materials (A and B). On both materials it appears that base proliferation rate are unaffected by STRO presence (A: $r = 2.04 \pm 0.23$ day⁻¹ without STRO vs. $r = 1.96 \pm 0.24$ day⁻¹ with STRO, B: $r = 2.18 \pm 0.11$ day⁻¹ vs. $r = 2.21 \pm 0.12$ day⁻¹) but limiting cell densities are reliably lowered (A: $c = 0.230 \pm 0.058$ μm^{-2} without STRO vs. $c = 0.037 \pm 0.017$ day⁻¹ with STRO, B: $c = 0.106 \pm 0.011$ μm^{-2} vs. $c = 0.0521 \pm 0.0076$ day⁻¹ corr.) that re-veals the ability of STRO presence to inhibit microbial proliferation is statistically significant 95% (A: $p = 0.9654$, B: $p = 0.9965$).

Keywords: biomaterial cytotoxicity, statistical methods, cell culture

Acknowledgement: Funded by Horizon 2020 project # 760921 (PANBioRA).

W.5.1 – Convolutional Neural Networks for Fibroblast Cell Classification and Counting - Arban Uka^{1*}, Julien Barthes², Xhoena Polisi¹, Aleksandros Ruci¹, Albana Halili^{1,3}, Ali Osman Topal¹, Nihal Engin Vrana⁴

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Abstract:

Convolutional neural networks (CNN) have become a primary choice in cell classification and counting because of the large volume of data that needs a proper and fast analysis. Multimedia elements (image and video) are analyzed for the investigation of cell parameters for the biomaterial risk assessment. Here we introduce a new fibroblast cell dataset and analyze it in detail using CNN and local binary patterns (LBP). Dataset is composed of nearly 20.000 images of cells in contact with favorable and toxic biomaterials and was separated in a training, testing a validation sets. CNN parameters (number of kernels per convolutional layer, kernel size, dropout rate etc) are optimized for this specific dataset and after the training, an accuracy of 95% is achieved in determining the health condition of the cells. Large images are composed of three major components: i) nuclei, ii) cytoplasm and iii) background. LBP of these three components has been evaluated and support vector machine is used to classify the LBP values that are then used to count the cell nuclei. Counting directly the nuclei circumvents the difficulty that stems from the deformable shape of the cytoplasm and the overlap of cytoplasm of different cells. An accuracy of 93% is achieved in counting.

Keywords: biomaterial risk assessment, deep learning, cell classification, counting

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 760921 (PANBioRA).

W.5.2 – Coupling experimental data and numerical simulation in modelling epithelial barrier formation with A549 cancerous cell line - Tijana Šušteršič^{1,2,3*}, Milica Nikolić^{1,3}, Julien Barthes⁴, Nihal Engin Vrana⁴, Nenad Filipović^{1,2,3}

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Abstract:

The overall aim of organ-on-a-chip monitoring model tissues is providing self-reporting tissue models that can either individually or as an integrated platform be used to test the biocompatibility of materials with some emphasis on materials immune-compatibility/immune-toxicity. We will focus in this abstract on coupling the experimental data with numerical simulations for the purposes of epithelial barrier formation with A549 cancerous cell line. The collected data included pictures, which have been acquired using bright field microscope at different time points: 30min, 4h, 24h, 48h and 72h, for calculation of the spreading and proliferation coefficient of A549 cell line. Developed model will provide insight into cells formation of the epithelial barrier. Calculated input parameters – characteristics of the chosen cell line: spreading and proliferation coefficients, seem appropriate and in accordance to the experimental outputs. Cells growth, migration and proliferation are modelled with a sort of extended diffusion equation. The preferred result of the simulation is time needed for formation of the barrier. This model will further become more complex in the view of getting desired outputs.

Keywords: A549 cell line, epithelial barrier, numerical simulations, image analysis

Acknowledgement: This research is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 760921 - PANBioRA. This article reflects only the author's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This study was also funded by the grants from the Serbian Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development III41007 and OI174028.

W.5.3 – Computer Assisted Spheroid Formation Analysis - Xhoena Polisi¹, Constantin-Edi Tanase², Arban Uka^{1*}, Nihal Engin Vrana³, Amir Ghaemmaghami²

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Abstract:

Computer assisted techniques could enable the use of morphological characteristics of hepatic spheroids as surrogate for their response to various stimuli. The aim of this work is to develop an automatic analysis procedure able to correctly acquire all the important morphological parameters of the hepatic spheroids under steady and after stimulation conditions. Within the datasets, several issues can occur related to the non uniform illumination background and inherent limitation in counting the exact object number when two or more are adjacent. Some of the images include patterns with intensity comparable to the spheroid intensity, such as extended grooves, and they are filtered out based on their eccentricity values. Traditional methods such as Otsu threshold does not segment the spheroid images truthfully due to their energy minimization based approach. To circumvent this limitation initially background removal is applied as a preprocessing step. Filters applied for this depend on the relative size of the spheroids in order not to diminish the image quality. Therefore, we propose a guided automatic threshold value that can differ the background and the spheroids more accurately by finding the critical peak on the pixel intensity histogram. Pixel intensity histograms are composed of three modes and the local minimum after the peak at the lowest values

is the threshold value. After applying the new guided thresholding technique, watershed algorithm is used in order to determine the separating nodes between objects that are contiguous to each-other. After this step, the total area covered by the spheroids is appropriately determined for all the images. Employing the above steps; the number, area and the perimeter of the spheroids; were correctly determined.

Keywords: Spheroid culture, segmentation, guided thresholding

Acknowledgement: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 760921 (PANBioRA).

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